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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com
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Assessing E-Leadership Readiness among Academic Leaders in Yantai, China

Yanjun Gao

*Doctor of Education Student
National University Manila*

Abstract

This study aims to explore the e-leadership readiness of academic leaders in Yantai City, Shandong Province. In this study, a quantitative method was used to collect data from 90 deans and executive boards of 3 schools in Shandong Province. The study aims to determine the readiness of academic leaders in the region for e-leadership and their familiarity with e-leadership practices, particularly in the field of information management. The study found that respondents had a deep understanding of e-leadership approaches in the field of information management, and that school administrators were perceived to have high e-leadership practices overall. However, the areas for improvement are in the areas of ethics and sharing, which suggests that these areas need improvement. The study concluded that the e-leadership practices of school administrators were generally consistent across years of service, and respondents' assessments of e-leadership practices did not differ significantly by age, gender, education, and position.

Key words: e-leadership, academic leaders, management, strategic planning, china

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